

ELECTROCHEMICAL ASPECTS OF RUBBER LATEX, COMPOUNDING INGREDIENTS AND THEIR MIXTURES

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The electrophoretic speeds of rubber latex particles as well as of the colloiddally dispersed compounding agents, e. g., zinc oxide, sulphur, China clay and of mixtures of them as are generally employed in baths for electrodeposition, have been measured in a microcataphoresis cell of the Northrup-Kunitz type. ζ -Potential of latex, calculated from the electrophoretic speeds, is considerably influenced by the presence of the compounding agents. Sulphur sol having the lowest ζ -potential tends to reduce that of latex as well as of others in a mixture, whereas zinc oxide and China clay, which have higher ζ -potentials, tend to increase the value for latex. A mixture of zinc oxide and China clay shows the highest (60 mV) ζ -potential compared to latex itself ($\zeta = 28.8$ mV). The isoelectric point of rubber latex was measured by calculating ζ -potential from electrophoretic speed at different pH values, which were maintained by means of Na_2CO_3 - $NaHCO_3$ buffers at the higher range and acetate buffers at the lower range. The I. P. was 4.2 and was lowered in presence of zinc oxide and China clay sols to 3.0 and 3.8 respectively, but increased to 5.1 in presence of sulphur sol.

The negative charge of rubber particles in Hevea latex has been demonstrated by a number of workers (Henry, *compt. rend.*, 1907, 144, 431; Sheppard, *Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1937, 52, 47; Kemp and Twiss, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, 32, 890; Blow, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1938, 57, 116T) and has been taken advantage of in the electrodeposition of rubber from latex bath. The ingredients of latex bath are quite numerous and include substances like sulphur, zinc oxide, China clay, wetting agents etc., each having a more or less specific role to play. The influence of these ingredients on the mobilities of rubber particles has not been properly assessed, although it is known that electrodeposition is affected by the added substances to an appreciable extent. The influence of small amounts of electrolytes (Sheppard, *loc. cit.*) and wetting agents (Blow, *loc. cit.*) on the electrophoretic mobility of rubber particles was noted by several workers.

In the present investigation, some of the ingredients of the bath, e. g., China clay, sulphur and zinc oxide, were obtained in the colloidal form and the electrophoretic mobility was measured individually and in mixtures of them, both amongst themselves and with latex. One of the objects of this study was to assess, if possible, the individual effect of the ingredients or mixtures of them on the electrophoretic mobility or ζ -potential and subsequently on electrodeposition of latex. The electrodeposition of rubber finds, as is well known, industrial applications in the preparation of microporous rubber (Flint, "The Chemistry and Technology of Rubber Latex", pp. 441, 561).

EXPERIMENTAL

Hevea latex, used in the present study, was obtained in a concentrated form from South India. The colloid content was determined by evaporating and drying a known volume of the suspension at $75^\circ \pm 2^\circ$. The latex was suitably diluted for subsequent experiments.

China clay was boiled with dilute HCl, washed free of acid and then peptised with ammonium hydroxide. The sol was diluted to 3%. 1% Zinc oxide sol was prepared

by mixing 1 part zinc oxide, 1 part water and 1% ammonium caesinate on dry weight of zinc oxide and then by requisite dilution. Colloidal sulphur (0.02%) was prepared by pouring a saturated solution of sulphur in absolute alcohol to a large volume of distilled water, and then removing as much alcohol as possible.

Measurement of Cataphoretic Speed and Electrokinetic Potential

The speed of the colloidal particles was measured at 0.79 depth in a microcataphoresis cell, designed by Abramson in modification of Northrup-Kunitz type. The ζ -potential was calculated by the simple Helmholtz relation :

$$\zeta = \frac{4 \pi \eta c A d (300)^2}{D i R t}$$

where, η = viscosity of the medium (0.01 poise approximately); D = dielectric constant of the medium (80); A = cross-section of the electrophoretic cell (0.073 cm²); i = current in amperes; c = cell constant (0.224); d = length of 50 divisions of the scale of the microscope (0.0417 cm.); t = time in seconds required to move 50 divisions; R = resistance in ohms of the sol measured in the conductivity cell.

The calculated ζ -potentials of sols, diluted 10 to 100 times, are shown in Table I. The p_H was measured with the help of a glass electrode.

TABLE I

Colloidal sol.	Conc.	p_H .	ζ -Potential.
Latex	0.034 %	8.1	28.8 mV
China clay	0.5	8.8	37.7
Zinc oxide	0.1	8.2	33.6
Sulphur	0.02	7.2	25.8

The dilute sols were mixed together in equal volumes and ζ -potentials were measured as usual. In mixtures containing latex as one of the ingredients, the particles which were singled out for velocity measurement were invariably those of latex. In the first four mixtures, recorded in Table II, the China clay particles could be easily spotted for measurement.

TABLE II

Mixtures of sols.	p_H .	ζ -Potential (mV).
China clay + sulphur	8.2	27.3 (China clay)
Zinc oxide + sulphur	7.3	29.5 "
China clay + sulphur + zinc oxide.	7.6	24.3 "
China clay + zinc oxide	8.0	35.3 "
Latex + China clay	7.1	48.3 (latex)
Latex + zinc oxide	7.6	49.8 "
Latex + China clay + zinc oxide	7.4	60.2 "
Latex + sulphur	7.8	28.1 "
Latex + sulphur + zinc oxide	7.9	29.7 "
Latex + sulphur + China clay	8.4	32.3 "
Latex + sulphur + China clay + zinc oxide	8.3	35.6 "

Isoelectric p_H of Latex

The variation of the cataphoretic speed of the rubber particles with p_H , individually and in mixture with some of the colloidal compounding ingredients, was measured by using various buffer solutions ranging from p_H 1 to 10. Sodium carbonate-bicarbonate buffers were employed in the alkaline range, while the acetate buffers were used in the acid range. For lower p_H , a hydrochloric acid solution was used. With the exception of the concentrated solutions having very low p_H , the ionic concentration was maintained at 0.01 N. The results are graphically shown in Fig. 1, from which the isoelectric p_H is found out to be 4.2.

DISCUSSION

The ζ -potential of latex and the compounding ingredients appears to decrease in the order: China clay, zinc oxide, latex, sulphur, which is also the decreasing order of the p_H of the suspensions.

An examination of the graph in Fig. 1 reveals that sulphur sol, which has the lowest potential amongst the compounding ingredients, lowers the ζ -potential of the others by its presence.

FIG. 1

A mixture of zinc oxide and China clay sol has an intermediate potential, but in presence of sulphur the potential is considerably lowered. In presence of both China clay as well as zinc oxide, the ζ -potential of latex increases and reaches the highest value when the three are present together. But the addition of sulphur to all these mixtures markedly lowers the ζ -potential. The ζ -potential of sulphur is of course increased in presence of others.

The isoelectric point of latex is found to be 4.2, which is somewhat higher than the value (3.7) observed by Subramanyan, Ghosh and Rao (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1948, **7B**, 77). This is lowered to p_H 3.0 and 3.8 respectively in presence of zinc oxide and China clay sols but increased to 5.1 in presence of sulphur sol which destabilises the latex, as has been shown by the potential measurements. The effect of zinc oxide and China clay sols is to stabilise the latex towards acids. Zinc oxide lowers the isoelectric point to a greater extent than China clay. This is perhaps due to the presence in zinc oxide

of ammonium caesinate, which is a greater stabilising agent than ammonia present in China clay. The destabilising effect of sulphur sol may be partly due to the presence of a little alcohol that could not be removed from it.

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